

INFINITY: Multidimensional knowledge-based annotation for ethical context-aware heritage data life cycles

D1.1 Project Handbook

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Contributors	
Deliverable reviews	All partners

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1 Project information

Project start date: 1st January 2026

Project Duration: 42 months

Project website: <https://infinity-eccch.eu/#>

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1.2 INFINITY Consortium

No.	Short name	Institution name	Country
1	UNIBO	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM – Università di Bologna	Italy
1.1	CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	Italy
2	SPA	Storypact GMBH	Austria
3	UNI JENA	Friedrich-Schiller Universität Jena	Germany
4	EF	Stichting Europeana	Netherlands
5	NISV	Stichting Nederlands Instituut Voorbeeld en Geluid	Netherlands
6	TMO	Time Machine Organization (TMO)	Austria
7	PSNC	Instytut Chemii Bioorganicznej Polskiej Akademii Nauk	Poland
8	DP	Digital Paths SRL	Italy
9	F&F DS	Facts & Files Digital Services GMBH	Germany
9.1	F&F PartG	Facts & Files - Historisches Forschungsinstitut Berlin Draushke	Germany
10	MIC	Ministero della Cultura	Italy
11	UEDIN	The University of Edinburgh	United Kingdom
12	Uwr	Uniwersytet Wroclawski	Poland
13	EIT-CC-SW	EIT Culture & Creativity South West SL	Spain
14	EPFL	Ecole Polytechnique Federale de Lausanne	Switzerland
15	AIT	Ait Austrian Institute of Technology GMBH	Austria

2 Project Summary

INFINITY is designed to serve as a core intelligence engine for the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH). The project addresses a critical limitation in current digitisation efforts: Cultural Heritage Digital Objects (CHDOs) are frequently trapped in fragmented silos with "flat" metadata, stripping them of their rich historical, social, and legal contexts. INFINITY advances the ECCCH by providing an innovative digital ecosystem of open-source tools and methods that shift the paradigm from static digital objects to dynamic, interconnected Multidimensional Knowledge Graphs (mKGs).

Key Innovations and Technologies: To achieve this transformation, INFINITY leverages cutting-edge Artificial Intelligence (including multilingual entity linking, automated transcription, and semantic enrichment) alongside advanced Semantic Web technologies. These tools are provided as highly interoperable plugins and RESTful APIs, designed to integrate smoothly into the existing Collection Management Systems (CMS) of cultural institutions. Crucially, the project operates under a "Ethics by Design" framework. INFINITY's automated ethical validation tools ensure that data pushed to the ECCCH is systematically checked for Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) compliance, cultural sensitivity, and AI bias. This guarantees that the resulting multidimensional representations are not only FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) but also transparent and legally safe for downstream reuse.

Validation and Use Cases The INFINITY ecosystem is co-designed and validated through six diverse, real-world use cases spanning multiple heritage domains:

1. **[CROWD]:** Supporting citizen science to transcribe and contextualize post-WWII handwritten artifacts.
2. **[4DGRID]:** Enabling geotemporal alignment and 4D visualization of historical images and maps.
3. **[MANUSCRIPTS]:** Harmonizing scattered metadata for historical texts into unified knowledge graphs.
4. **[AUDIOVISUAL]:** Enriching contemporary, time-based media while navigating complex privacy and copyright challenges.
5. **[ARCHIVE]:** Unlocking archival knowledge and clarifying reuse rights for creative professionals and the general public.
6. **[3DARCHEO]:** Standardising advanced open-air archaeological photographic surveys (RTI/3D) into FAIR semantic models.

Impact: Ultimately, INFINITY empowers Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs) of all sizes to smoothly upgrade their internal workflows and seamlessly onboard to the ECCCH. By generating transparent, ethically cleared, and deeply contextualized data, INFINITY bridges the gap between heritage preservation and economic growth, unlocking the vast potential of Europe's cultural assets for researchers, citizens, and the creative industries.

3 Executive Summary

This document provides the INFINITY consortium with guidelines on internal procedure for the monitoring of project activities and progress, quality assurance and risk management. It brings together a wide range of general operational information including contact details, operational and reporting processes, communication protocols, etcetera. Quality plan elements include information about standards, technical quality control, procedures for risk monitoring, decision-making, and conflict resolution. The quality plan also includes mechanisms for self-assessment including the peer review of deliverables.

This is a living document, although we submit a complete version, the project handbook must align with other procedural practices of the project that, in some case, will be finalised later, for example the RuleBook, the Ethical guidelines.

4 Document History

Version	Date	Summary of changes	Author(s)
0.1	05/03/2026	First draft	Valentina Presutti, Solmi Andrea
0.2	13/03/2026	Deliverable timeline changed, updated “internal and external communication”, “dissemination and communication requirements” and “Ethical Issues” sections.	Valentina Presutti, Solmi Andrea
0.3	30/03/2026	Template applied	Valentina Presutti
1.0	31/03/2026	Added Table of Content	Andrea Solmi

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5 Introduction

The kick-off meeting organised in Bologna (13-15 January 2026) was the first occasion for the project partners to discuss the planning of activities in each WP to guarantee an efficient and smooth running of activities. One of the aspects presented and discussed was the internal organisation of the consortium, including operational and reporting processes, communication protocols, and formation about standards, technical quality control, procedures for risk monitoring, decision-making, and conflict resolution. The following chapters summarise mainly the outcomes of the kick-off meeting that form the Project Quality Assurance and Risk Assessment Plan.

5.1 Project organization, roles and responsibilities

The management structure for INFINITY has several purposes: to ensure the involvement of all contractors in management decision-making; to provide a streamlined and efficient decision structure; to provide management and administration that will keep the project performing on time, quality and budget; and to provide a mechanism for the prevention of conflict and dispute resolution. The management structure is composed of the following bodies:

5.1.1 Project Coordinator

The Coordinator shall be the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority and shall perform all tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and in this Consortium Agreement (art. and in the Consortium Agreement (section 6.4).

In particular, the Coordinator shall be responsible for:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations under this Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement
- keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available
- collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables and specific requested documents to the Granting Authority
- transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned
- administering the financial contribution of the Granting Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks described in Section 7.2
- providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims
- providing a copy of the Grant Agreement and its Annexes to the Associated Partners.

5.1.2 General Assembly

The General Assembly is the steering and decision-making body of the Consortium. The GA is composed of one representative of each partner and chaired by the Coordinator. Each member has one vote. The decision-making at the meetings will be based on majority voting (2/3 of the votes).

The GA decides on (Consortium Agreement A Section 6.3.1.2):

.. (i) Content, finances and intellectual property rights

- Proposals for changes to Annexes 1 and 2 of the Grant Agreement to be agreed by the Granting Authority such as changes resulting from suggested reallocation of tasks and budget by the Executive Board
- The percentage of work package completion per work package as well as per Party to be reported to the Granting Authority based on the assessment by the Executive Board regarding the individual performance of single Parties in case of non-completion of work packages.
- Modifications or withdrawal of Background in Attachment 1 (Background Included)
- Additions to Attachment 3 (List of Third Parties for simplified transfer according to Section 8.3.2)
- [Additions to Attachment 4 (Identified entities under the same control)]

.. (ii) Evolution of the consortium

- Entry of a new Party to the Project and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession of such a new Party
- Withdrawal of a Party from the Project and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of the withdrawal
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for a change of the Coordinator
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for suspension of all or part of the Project
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for termination of the Project and the Consortium Agreement

.. (iii) Breach, defaulting party status and litigation

- Identification of a breach by a Party of its obligations under this Consortium Agreement or the Grant Agreement
- Declaration of a Party to be a Defaulting Party
- Remedies to be performed by a Defaulting Party
- Termination of a Defaulting Party's participation in the consortium and measures relating thereto
- Steps to be taken for litigation purposes and the coverage of litigation costs in case of joint claims of the parties of the consortium against a Party (e.g. Section 7.1.4)

Ordinary meetings of the General Assembly will be planned at least once a year. The chairperson shall also convene extraordinary meetings at any time upon written request of 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly.

The current list of the members of the General Assembly can be found in the table below. Any modifications must be communicated to the projected coordinator and project manager:

No.	Short name	General Assembly Member	Email
1	UNIBO	Valentina Presutti	valentina.presutti@unibo.it
1.1	CNR	Andrea Nuzzolese	andreagiovanni.nuzzolese@cnr.it
2	SPA	Lyndon Nixon	nixon@storypact.com
3	UNI JENA	Dominik Ukolov	dominik.ukolov@uni-jena.de

4	EF	Emma Collins	emma.collins@europeana.eu
5	NISV	Johan Oomen	joomen@beeldengeluid.nl
6	TMO	Kevin Baumer	kevin.baumer@timemachine.eu
7	PSNC	Alexandra Nowak	anowak@man.poznan.pl
8	DP	Antonio Puglisi	a.puglisi@digitalpaths.it
9	F&F DS	Frank Draushke	drauschke@ffdigitalservices.com
9.1	F&F PartG	Frank Draushke	drauschke@ffdigitalservices.com
10	MIC	Chiara Veninata	chiara.veninata@cultura.gov.it
11	UEDIN	Melissa Terras	m.terras@ed.ac.uk
12	Uwr	Adam Poznański	adam.poznanski@uwr.edu.pl
13	EIT-CC-SW	Fabio Palma	fabio.palma@eit-culture-creativity.eu
14	EPFL	Frédéric Kaplan	frederic.kaplan@epfl.ch
15	AIT	Sergiu Gordea	sergiu.gordea@ait.ac.at

5.1.3 Executive Board

The Executive Board is the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, and it shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly. The Executive Board shall consist of the Coordinator (UNIBO), SPA, JENA, NISV and PCSS. The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the Executive Board, unless decided otherwise by a majority of two-thirds.

The Executive Board shall:

- Keep track of the effective and efficient overall implementation of the Project, based on the Consortium Plan, particularly regarding the completion of the work package activities in tasks and deliverables of each Party (see Section 4.5 of the Consortium Agreement).
- Prepare the meetings, propose decisions and prepare the agenda of the General Assembly according to Section 6.3.1.2 of the Consortium Agreement.
- Be responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly.
- Support the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the Granting Authority and in preparing related information and deliverables
- Prepare the content and timing of press releases and joint publications by the consortium or proposed by the Granting Authority in respect of the procedures of the Grant Agreement Article 17 and Annex 5 Section “Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility” and of Section 8 of this Consortium Agreement.
- Evaluate suggestions of the Work Package Leaders Group for the reallocation of tasks and budget in work packages.
- Make suggestions for amendments to Annex 1 and Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement to the General Assembly, especially if restructuring is required to enable the finalisation of non-completed work packages or in case of termination of a Party;
- Assess reports presented by each Work Package Leader, which have been compiled by the Work Package Leader based on the Internal Progress Reports;

- Assess the status or completion of each work package and prepare the periodic reporting for the work packages together with the Coordinator;
- Propose payment instalments to the Coordinator according to the outcomes of these assessments (see Section 7.2.2 of the Consortium Agreement);
- Support the Coordinator in the collection of information regarding the termination report and amendment procedures in case of termination of a Party’s participation;
- Inform the General Assembly of an alleged breach in performance or reporting (see Section 4.5) within the breach procedure under Section 4.2 of the Consortium Agreement;
- Suggest performance indicators for the determination of proper completion of work packages to the General Assembly.

The current list of the members of the Executive Board can be found in the table below. Any modifications must be communicated to the projected coordinator and project manager:

No.	Short name	Executive Board Member	Email
1	UNIBO	Valentina Presutti	valentina.presutti@unibo.it
2	SPA	Lyndon Nixon	nixon@storypact.com
3	UNI JENA	Dominik Ukolov	dominik.ukolov@uni-jena.de
5	NISV	Johan Oomen	joomen@beeldengeluid.nl
7	PSNC	Aleksandra Nowak	anowak@man.poznan.pl

5.1.4 Work Package Leaders Group

The Work Package Leaders Group is the supervisory body for the activities carried out in the respective WPs.

The Work Package Leaders Group shall consist of the Coordinator and Work Package Leaders.

The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the Work Package Leaders Group, unless decided otherwise by a majority of two-thirds.

The Work Package Leaders Group shall:

- Coordinate activities related to the work packages.
- Update the General Assembly on relevant information and issues related to the work packages.
- Meet before each Executive Board meeting and provide a report on the progress of the tasks, informing about any expected or possible deviations, or other relevant information concerning the execution of the Workplan.

The current list of the members of the Work Package Leaders Group can be found in the table below. Any modifications must be communicated to the projected coordinator and project manager:

Work Package n.	Work Package name	WP leader	Email
1-3	Project Management and Coordination	UNIBO – Valentina Presutti, Solmi Andrea	valentina.presutti@unibo.it
4	Assessing collection management practices and benchmarking technical approaches	SPA – Lyndon Nixon	nixon@storypact.com
5	Use Case Requirements and Design	UNI JENA – Dominik Ukolov	dominik.ukolov@uni-jena.de
6	Scale Up and Deployment: Use Case Implementation	PCSS – Aleksandra Nowak	anowak@man.poznan.pl
7	Scale up and Deployment: Use Case Validation	PCSS – Aleksandra Nowak	anowak@man.poznan.pl
8	INFINITY ecosystem for multi-context CHDO: Ethics-driven requirements and design	UEDIN – Melissa Terras	m.terras@ed.ac.uk
9	INFINITY ecosystem for multi-context CHDO: software components implementation	UNIBO – Valentina Presutti	valentina.presutti@unibo.it
10	INFINITY ecosystem for multi-context CHDO: software components deployment and evaluation	UNIBO – Valentina Presutti	valentina.presutti@unibo.it
11-12	Integration with the DS4CH and ECCCH	EF – Valentine Charles, Antoine Isaac, Emma Collins	valentine.charles@europeana.eu antoine.isaac@europeana.eu emma.collins@europeana.eu
13	INFINITY methodology and training materials	NISV– Johan Oomen	joomen@beeldengeluid.nl
14-16	Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation	DP – Francesca Brizi	francesca.brizi4@unibo.it

5.1.5 Technical Board

The Technical Board is the consortium body charged with the coordination necessary for the software implementation.

The Technical Board shall consist of one representative of each Party and at least one representative participating in the integration task force coordinated by ECHOES.

SPA, together with the Coordinator (UNIBO), will coordinate the Technical Board.

The Coordinator or SPA shall chair all meetings of the Executive Board, unless decided otherwise by a majority of two-thirds.

The Technical Board shall:

- Supervise the technical development of the INFINITY digital ecosystem (software components) making sure that synergies are identified in a timely manner and issues around compatibility and technical interoperability are addressed harmonically during the development phase;
- Define the common methodological approach and identify the supporting collaborative tools to be used, and release guidelines through a Rule Book;
- Design and release the overall architecture of the ecosystem's software components, defining the APIs required to support their release as web services and the development of CMS platform plugins;
- Ensure that all the developed components are released according to the FAIR principles, documented (for WP13) and respect the alignment and integration constraints identified by WP11-12 for interoperability with the ECCCH and DS4CH;
- Update the General Assembly on relevant information regarding the afore-mentioned tasks.

The current list of the members of the Technical Board can be found in the table below. Any modifications must be communicated to the projected coordinator and project manager:

No.	Short name	Technical Board Member	Email
1	UNIBO	Luana Bulla	luana.bulla@unibo.it
1.1	CNR	Andrea Nuzzolese	andreagiovanni.nuzzolese@cnr.it
2	SPA	Lyndon Nixon	nixon@storypact.com
3	UNI JENA	Dominik Ukolov	dominik.ukolov@uni-jena.de
4	EF	Hugo Manguinhas	hugo.manguinhas@europeana.eu
5	NISV	Johan Oomen	joomen@beeldengeluid.nl
6	TMO	Kevin Baumer	kevin.baumer@timemachine.eu
7	PCSS	Alexandra Nowak	anowak@man.poznan.pl
8	DP	Antonio Puglisi	a.puglisi@digitalpaths.it
9	F&F DS	Frank Draushke	drauschke@ffdigitalservices.com
9.1	F&F PartG	Frank Draushke	drauschke@ffdigitalservices.com
10	MIC	Chiara Veninata	chiara.veninata@cultura.gov.it
11	UEDIN	Andrea Kocsis	akocsis@ed.ac.uk
12	Uwr	Adam Poznański	adam.poznanski@uwr.edu.pl
13	EIT-CC-SW	Fabio Palma	fabio.palma@eit-culture-creativity.eu
14	EPFL	Frédéric Kaplan	frederic.kaplan@epfl.ch
15	AIT	Sergiu Gordea	sergiu.gordea@ait.ac.at

5.1.6 Other key roles

Project Manager – Andrea Solmi (UNIBO)

The Project manager assist the coordinator in the day-by-day management of the GA, supports the coordinator with the collection of reports and deliverables, assists the coordinator in the management of the project, supports partners for administrative and legal issues, supports the organization, preparation and follow up of periodical meetings, support the partners with reference to procedures requested by the European Commission.

6 Deliverables and reports

6.1 Procedures for the preparation and submission of deliverables

The following procedure defines the timeline and responsibilities for the preparation, internal review, and submission of project deliverables, to ensure their quality and timely submission.

- **90 days before the deliverable deadline:** two internal reviewers from the consortium are selected. The reviewers must not be directly involved in the writing of the deliverable, to ensure an independent review. The Task Leader notifies the Work Package Leader of the selected reviewers.
- **60 days before the deadline:** the Task Leader prepares and submits an outline of the deliverable to the Work Package Leader and the Project Coordinator. The document is uploaded to the project's shared platform, and the link is shared with the Work Package Leader and the Coordinator.
- **30 days before the deadline:** a near-final draft of the deliverable is shared with the reviewers. This version should be complete in terms of content, with only minor revisions still pending.
- **20 days before the deadline:** the reviewers provide their feedback to the Task Leader.
- **10 days before the deadline:** the Task Leader shares the final revised version of the deliverable with the reviewers, incorporating the received comments.
- **7 days before the deadline:** the reviewers perform the final validation of the document.
- **5 days before the deadline:** the final version of the deliverable is submitted to the Project Coordinator for official submission.

Following the decision taken by the General Assembly during the **Kick-off Meeting**, all deliverables originally scheduled for Month 14 (M14) will be anticipated to Month 12 (M12).

6.2 Criteria for Reviewers

In the INFINITY project, deliverables span a diverse range of formats: from core technological assets to comprehensive research documents. All of them must be accompanied by a formal written report. To guarantee excellence and interoperability, the project enforces a dual-track quality assurance process. Any deliverable containing software or ontologies must undergo a rigorous evaluation by the Technical Board, utilising specific, pre-defined technical criteria in line with the RuleBook, before

it can be officially released into the INFINITY Ecosystem. Concurrently, all scientific and technical reports are held to a journal-ready standard. These documents are subjected to rigorous peer review mirroring the highest academic standards, ensuring that INFINITY’s methodological robustness and scientific claims are validated by the community before submission. The review criteria include: 1) clarity and structure; 2) Methodological rigor; 3) Context and State of the Art; 4) Results and Validation; 5) Ethical and fairness.

Reviewers are provided with a deliverable form by the task leader. The deliverable template form is available at: [Infinity Deliverable Peer Review Form.docx](#)

Table 1 below shows the list of INFINITY deliverables with the revision timetable:

Del n.	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary	90 days before	60 days before	30 days before	10 days before	Due Date
D1.1	Project Handbook	UNIBO	-	31/01/26	28/02/26	21/03/26	31/03/26
D14.1	INFINITY image and public presence	DP	-	31/01/26	28/02/26	21/03/26	31/03/26
D1.2	Data Management Plan WP1	UNIBO	01/04/26	01/05/26	31/05/26	20/06/26	30/06/26
D4.1	Survey on collection management practices and systems	PSNC	01/04/26	01/05/26	30/05/26	20/06/26	30/06/26
D4.2	Survey on IPR regulations and business models involving CHDO	EF	01/04/26	01/05/26	30/05/26	20/06/26	30/06/26
D8.1	Guidelines on data ethics	UEDIN	01/04/26	01/05/26	30/05/26	20/06/26	30/06/26
D14.2	Plan for the Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication of results (PEDR) WP14	DP	01/04/26	01/05/26	30/05/26	20/06/26	30/06/26
D14.3	Capacity building workshops WP14	EIT-CC-SW	02/10/26	01/11/26	30/11/26	21/12/26	31/12/26
D1.3	Ethics requirements	UNIBO	02/10/26	01/11/26	30/11/26	21/12/26	31/12/26*
D4.3	Benchmark design and evaluation	SPA	02/10/26	01/11/26	30/11/26	21/12/26	31/12/26*
D5.1	Technical Roadmap	UNI JENA	02/10/26	01/11/26	30/11/26	21/12/26	31/12/26*
D5.2	Use case definition, formal requirements and design	UNI-JENA	02/10/26	01/11/26	30/11/26	21/12/26	31/12/26*
D8.2	Developers Rulebook WP8	SPA	02/10/26	01/11/26	30/11/26	21/12/26	31/12/26*
D8.3	Ethics-driven requirements and design for the INFINITY ecosystem	UEDIN	02/10/26	01/11/26	30/11/26	21/12/26	31/12/26*
D15.1	Plan for the Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication of results (PEDR) WP15	DP	31/03/27	01/04/27	01/06/27	20/06/27	30/06/27
D9.1	Release (Alpha) of the INFINITY ecosystem	SPA	02/05/27	02/06/27	01/07/27	21/07/27	31/07/27

All project periodic reports include a technical part and a financial part. Periodic Reports must be submitted 60 days after the end of reporting periods. As for the **Periodic report RP1**, as the General Assembly has decided to anticipate the submission of deliverables officially due at M14 to M12, we will proceed accordingly and **prepare RP1 between M12 and M14**.

The **technical part** includes an overview of the action implementation. It must be prepared using the template available in the Portal Periodic Reporting tool.

The **financial part** includes the consolidated financial statement for the whole consortium. The financial statement is automatically generated (based on the accepted work packages and the corresponding lump sum shares).

Periodic reports – technical part		
WHO	WHAT	WHEN
UNIBO	Share report template with all partners, with info on sections assignment	Before the end of each reporting period (before M12 due RP1)
WP leaders/Task leaders	Draft the assigned sections on the shared file	End of reporting period + 15 days (end of M12 + 15 days for RP1)
UNIBO/WP leaders	Submit review as comments on the draft report (back to the partners for further integration/modification)	End of reporting period + 28 days (end of M12 + 28 days for RP1)
WP leaders / Task leaders	Finalise contribution by addressing the comments received	End of reporting period + 35 days (end of M12 + 35 days for RP1)
UNIBO	Submission of final version	Within the deadline. It may vary according to the actual review date

6.4 Procedures for the update of the continuous reporting

The consortium is also required to report on a series of transversal aspects concerning the project against which the progress and success of the project will be evaluated. These aspects are included in the Continuous reporting module on the **Funding & tender opportunities portal** of the European commission:

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/myarea/projects>

The following information must be reported periodically or as scheduled directly in the Funding & tender portal. For each module the partner institution responsible for filling out the information is indicated:

- Project summary for publication – abstract (UNIBO)
- Submit deliverables (UNIBO)
- Report progress in achieving milestones (UNIBO+WP leaders)
- Critical risks follow-up (UNIBO+WP leaders)
- Dissemination and communication (UNIBO and WP leaders)
- Publications and dataset (UNIBO and WP leaders)
- Other details (about IPR, impact, results etc.) (UNIBO)

6.5 Project reviews

The reviews represent the key moment of the project when the progress, quality of results, future plans and overall success of the project are assessed by the HADEA agency with the help of independent experts (monitors). All periodic reports and deliverables submitted will be checked and evaluated by the HADEA officer and independent experts.

The presence of the project coordinator, project manager and WP leaders is required during the review meetings. Any other project members of the project could attend upon request.

The schedule and venues of project reviews is related to the periodic reports deadline:

- **1st Project Review:** March/April 2027 (after RP1 submission, it may vary)
- **2nd Project Review:** May/June 2028 (after RP2 submission, it may vary)
- **3rd Project Review:** August/September 2029 (after RP3 submission, it may vary)

6.6 Reporting and payment overview

The figure below shows an overview of the reporting and payment process.

Interim payments correspond to the shares of the lump sum set out in Annex 2 for the work packages completed and approved in the reporting period.

Interim payments pay the lump sum shares for completed work packages. Final payments can also pay partially completed work packages.

Figure 1 – reporting and payments (source: EC webinar)

7 Risk management

Risk is defined as the combination of the probability of an event negatively affecting any project activity and its consequences. Risks are intrinsic to any project and shall therefore be identified, controlled and neutralized since the very early stages of a project.

Management is a systematic process aiming to identify, assess, manage, monitor and report on risks, through the following actions:

- adopt risk criteria regarding events that could occur and may impact the project's scope, schedule, budget and performance;
- identify, analyse, and evaluate risk in order to optimize the contingency measures;
- develop and implement strategies to effectively prevent, contain, and eliminate obstacles to the project success;
- track, review and report on risk evolution to re-define strategies and priorities, and improve management process.

7.1 Risk management plan

The risk management plan is a living shared document available at [Risk-management.xlsx](#)¹.

Every team member has responsibility for managing risks within their own activities. However, given the managing structure of INFINITY, the key persons for a timely communication of risks are WP

¹ Link only accessible to project partners.

Leaders, who are identified as Risk Owners (RO). The risk management procedure will take the following steps:

- all ROs survey monthly the tasks and sub-tasks leaders of their WP to identify new risks or foreseen risks that have happened or may happen;
- In case of new risk or foreseen risk happening ROs (i.e.WP leaders) immediately update the live risk document at [Risk-management.xlsx](#), including a mitigation strategy proposal, and notify the Coordinator;
- the coordinator informs the EB about the status of risks. The EB sets up a risk mitigation strategy or decides to apply the mitigation strategy, if already foreseen;
- the risk document will be continuously updated by the ROs in each WP, allowing the coordinator to track the risk evolution towards its final conclusion;
- a short risk assessment session will be addressed during EB or WP leaders' meetings.

7.2 Identified risks

At the moment, the identified risks are listed in the following table, as described in the DoA – Part A table “List of critical risks”. WP leaders may update the initial risks list by adding new identified risks and inform the coordinator about them.

Risk Number	Description	WP No(s)	Proposed Mitigation Measures
1°	Consortium partner is unable to take up their responsibilities (low, medium)	All	The consortium is highly complementary, allowing us to source alternative competencies if a key skill is unavailable from a partner. The experienced project coordinator, previously leading the H2020 project POLIFONIA, will promptly identify and address any task or work package issues, proposing solutions to the Steering Committee.
2°	Ineffective interdisciplinary integration, leading to misaligned objectives (low, medium)	All	Cross-disciplinary meetings and a unified glossary, with oversight by an Interdisciplinary Working Group, are employed to ensure effective integration and collaboration across different fields.
3°	Partner problems (e.g., underperforming partner; a key partner leaves the project). (low, medium)	1,2,3	The well-balanced consortium includes organizations of various sizes with complementary expertise. Should any issues arise, such as a partner underperforming or leaving, the network will be leveraged to quickly address gaps and ensure successful project delivery.
4°	Overlap with R&I work within and beyond Horizon Europe might result in duplication of efforts. (medium, medium)	5	Related work in topic destinations "World-leading data and computing technologies" and "A human-centred and ethical development of digital and industrial technologies" is tracked in T5.1. Communication with projects that overlap technically are conducted to ensure complementary outcomes.
5°	Lack of content/data with the necessary variability/quantity (low, high)	6,7	Several technology and use case partners host extensive data repositories; active data interfaces to Wikidata and DS4CH (via EF); additional resources available via NISV and TMO members, and open data repositories; GDPR challenges for provision can be lowered by applying PET/anonymization.

6°	Integration of INFINITY components into the tools used in the use case fails (low, high)	6,7	While critical for the project objectives, integration problems are unlikely as we use well-established technologies for I/O (REST APIs) and partners are experienced in the integration task with others' systems.
7°	Use cases fail to validate the INFINITY results (low, high)	6,7	Use case stakeholders are involved from the very beginning in use case design and requirements solicitation. Regular rounds of feedback and adaptation ensure results closely address stakeholder needs.
8°	AI approaches not producing sufficient or required results (medium, low)	8,9,10	While new AI methods like GNNs are experimental, past successes suggest potential for future innovation. If one method falters, experienced partners can test alternative AI and graph approaches.
9°	Standards and specifications do not align to those used by INFINITY tools (medium, low)	8,9,10	The project initiates early definition of required extensions and proposals to specification bodies. EF, NISV, and PSNC, as active organizations in their domains, will lead in defining data specifications. It is noted that new tools often set precedents for specifications before wider adoption.
10°	Coordination with ECCCH delayed or takes a different approach (medium, low)	11,12	Coordination with ECHOES will be closely managed through PSNC and EF, via participation in the ECCCH Integration Task Force.
11°	Diss. and comm measures are ineffective, limiting the project's impact and adoption. (low, medium)	14,15,16	Partners have concrete, high-profile channels for dissemination and communication. Execution will be adaptive to changes in those channels and how external audiences react to our activities, modifying planned activities as necessary.

8 Conflict resolution

Conflicts will be resolved by a procedure detailed in the Consortium Agreement (Art. 11.8 Settlement of disputes). The partners shall endeavour to settle amicably any dispute, controversy or claim arising under, out of or relating to this Agreement and any subsequent amendments of this Agreement, including, without limitation, its formation, validity, binding effect, interpretation, performance, breach or termination, as well as non-contractual claims.

Potential conflicts should be brought to the immediate attention of the Project Coordinator by the WP leader concerned. The Project Coordinator may be involved in the conflict resolution if requested by a Party or by the Work package Leader. As a last resort, if any such dispute, controversy or claim has not been settled amicably, the courts of Brussels shall have exclusive jurisdiction (Art. 11.8 of the CA).

9 Internal and external communication

Shared space

All project partners have access to the INFINITY-ECCCH shared space, the reserved repository for partners we use to share all the documents related to the project. The repository is handled by UNIBO using Microsoft SharePoint and will be available for the project partners during the lifetime of the project and beyond.

The shared space is organised in different **folders** and it allows partners to store, find and work collaboratively on project documents, keep track of revisions and different versions released. It also includes a dedicated folder where the standard **Project_Templates** are stored (templates for deliverable, templates for reviews, technical reports, financial reports, risk report, agendas, minutes, presentations etc.). In the same folder, the partners can find the logo and media material of the project. In the main folder partners can find the file “INFINITY Team”. It is responsibility of all partners to keep this file updated to make sure all contacts of project participants are available for the whole team. This file includes also indication about the role of the member and the tasks they are involved in.

Each WP has its own folder, inside a subfolder for each task should be created. All documents, including early stage versions and presentations should be uploaded and shared in this repository to avoid fragmentation and help all members to access the project material.

WP groups

To guarantee an efficient communication among all project partners UNIBO has created a mailing list including all members of the project tem. To ensure that the communications reach the correct people involved in different parts of the project, UNIBO will create a set of mailing lists, one for each workpackage under request of the WP leaders:

- Project general mailing list: infinity-eccch@live.unibo.it
- Instruction to create a WP mailing list:
 - The WP leader collects all contacts of the partner’s reference persons involved in the WP
 - The WP leader sends a request to create the WP mailing list to minhdavide.ragagni3@unibo.it including
 - The WP number and title
 - The list of members
 - UNIBO will create the mailing list and communicate it to the WP leader

Meetings platform

For guaranteeing integration and homogeneity in the project coordination, the UNIBO Teams platform is made available to all partners for online meetings. Within the Team platform, under “Teams” every member that is part of the INFINITY group can see the “INFINITY-ECCCH” Team. This team includes separate channels that can be used for sharing files, organising online meetings, interacting through posts on the channel. A channel for each active WP has been created and it is connected with the corresponding folder in the shared space (accessible under the tab “Shared”). From the general channel, it is possible to access a shared calendar (tab “Calendar”), where all WP and task leaders are invited to post the scheduled events. This should

help avoiding conflicts in the meetings' organisation and shall give all partners the opportunity to check the project schedule and join the meetings they are involved in.

Member accounts

All members are registered in the project groups with their institutional accounts and, in addition, for each member a UNIBO account will be created and added to the groups they are involved in. The unibo account shall guarantee access to wider functionalities to the platform, when restrictions are set on external accounts, and will guarantee access to ALMAWIFI, the wireless network of the University of Bologna, every time they will visit the UNIBO facilities.

To be added to the project groups or any other group, a request must be sent to minhdavide.ragagni3@unibo.it to create an account and be added to the project groups and other possible groups of interest. A form with personal data will be required to be filled. The provided data will be treated by the University of Bologna exclusively for the time and purpose necessary to manage the account, in compliance with GDPR.

10 Dissemination and communication requirements

The Consortium Agreement signed by all partners foresees in Art 8.3 the procedures and rules for the dissemination of own results, dissemination of another partner's unpublished results or background as well as cooperation obligations.

Moreover, the Consortium Agreement includes specific rules and procedures regarding the use of confidential information by partners (CA Section 10 Non-disclosure of information).

10.1 Acknowledgement of funding and disclaimers

All partners should always indicate that the project received funding from the EU by including the following statement together with a high resolution EU flag:

“INFINITY project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe CL2-2024-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01 under Grant Agreement No 101233051”.

All partners should include the following statement to acknowledge EU funding in scientific publications and dissemination activities: “This research is supported by INFINITY: a EU Horizon Europe project under Grant Agreement No 101233051”.

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains by including the following disclaimers:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EC-REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

10.2 Logos

All communication and dissemination material produced in INFINITY project (for internal and external use) must show both the EU logo and the INFINITY logo, available in the Logo folder in the member area.

The rules for displaying the EU logo and formats are available in the guidelines “The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes”: https://ec.europa.eu/info/files/use-eu-emblem-context-eu-programmes-2021-2027_en

11 Ethical issues

11.1 Use of generative AI

The INFINITY approach to the use of generative AI follows the UNIBO policy for ethical and responsible use of Generative AI in research and training activities. We report here the key principles and guidelines that are relevant to the INFINITY project and that the INFINITY team shall comply with.

The INFINITY team recognizes Generative AI (GenAI) as a tool capable of stimulating novel, creative, and experimental approaches. This Policy outlines the principles and guidelines through which we intend to promote an effective and responsible use of GenAI to support research and development, ensuring the essential values of quality, scientific integrity, and personal protection.

The guidelines set forth by this Policy aim to ensure that GenAI is:

- Used responsibly and consciously;
- Employed to contribute to improving the quality of research, including in collaborations with society and businesses;
- Used in service of people, rather than as a substitute for their creative and intellectual activities.

Based on mutual trust and openness to change, we consider the use of GenAI legitimate. We do not adopt measures aimed at prohibiting or monitoring its use, in the belief that adherence to our shared values and principles on research Integrity are sufficient to ensure that every member of the community acts with responsibility and awareness of the opportunities and risks of GenAI, thereby avoiding improper or harmful

11.2 Principles

- Human-centricity, understood as active supervision and critical capacity on the part of the user, so that GenAI may serve as a support to enhance individual intuition, creativity, judgment, and decision-making.

- Honesty and transparency, understood as personal awareness and, where required, explicit acknowledgment of GenAI's contribution to the creation of the final output.
- Accountability, understood as the assumption of responsibility by the user and the ability to account for results generated through GenAI systems, which must be duly subjected to active supervision and critical evaluation.
- Accuracy, understood as a commitment to adopt verification procedures for results that are appropriate to the specific use case, while remaining mindful of the risks inherent in using GenAI tools.
- Respect for rights, society, and the environment, including privacy and individual rights, the protection of any intellectual property rights regarding information entered into the system to generate output and the results generated by GenAI tools, as well as respect for the values of equity, inclusiveness, and environmental sustainability.

11.3 Individual responsibility

- **Consider, when resorting to GenAI tools, the environmental impacts** resulting from the significant energy consumption required for the training and execution of tasks.
- Refrain from the substantial use of GenAI tools in activities that could have repercussions for other individuals or organizations, such as peer review.
- **Be aware of the primary characteristics of the GenAI tools used**, as these may affect the correctness of the generated outputs, and adopt appropriate mitigation measures accordingly. An example of a characteristic that can impact the reproducibility of results is the probabilistic nature of GenAI models. In this case, an appropriate mitigation measure is the verification of primary sources and critical supervision of the generated output.
- **Verify the contractual conditions and privacy options provided by GenAI tools** to understand who holds the rights to the generated output (which may sometimes be reserved for the system provider) and what the privacy compliance requirements are. The latter may vary depending on the environment in which the GenAI tool operates (e.g., closed environments, hosting on third-party infrastructure with guaranteed privacy, or open platforms accessible via the internet).
- **Do not provide online GenAI systems with the personal data of third parties**, including special categories of data such as health or genetic data, unless the data subject has given their consent or there is another appropriate legal basis for doing so.
- **Do not input confidential information into GenAI systems**, such as protected or sensitive data (even if non-personal), information subject to non-disclosure agreements with third parties, or non-public corporate strategy data, unless adequate system guarantees ensure data confidentiality.
- **Be aware that the GenAI system is not a legal entity** and cannot be held responsible or considered the author/co-author of the generated output.
- **Examine the accuracy and validity of outputs produced with GenAI** to identify and correct potential errors, including factual inaccuracies, logical fallacies, or inappropriate or potentially offensive language.
- **Be aware that AI-generated output may not comply with copyright law**, as it may rely on copyrighted works without the author's authorisation.

- **Conduct appropriate checks to ensure that products do not constitute plagiarism**, especially when GenAI is used substantially to generate, expand, or rework content.
- **Respect the work of others** and cite it in your own writings, considering that the output of GenAI tools may be based on results achieved by other people. Each individual using GenAI assumes full responsibility for the accuracy and consistency of the produced output and is accountable for any potential plagiarism.
- **Protect unpublished work** (both your own and others') by refraining from inputting it into GenAI systems, unless there are adequate guarantees that the data will remain confidential. For example, that it will not be reused to train future language models or be subject to untraceable and unverifiable reuse.
- **Do not input information into the system for which a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) has been signed.**
- **Exercise caution when using synthetic data**, i.e., data generated by GenAI from examples or textual descriptions rather than obtained from real-world sampling. Ensure that in research products based on the analysis or processing of such data, their synthetic nature is explicitly declared, and that testing measures have been implemented to verify that results based on synthetic data are reasonably sensible in the real world.
- **Verify that content produced by GenAI correctly cites sources** and includes appropriate references or other attributions for the information used.
- **Declare the substantial use of GenAI in research and development activities.** In any case, verify and adhere to any specific indications on the responsible use of GenAI contained in agreements entered into with third parties, such as contracts with publishers, the EU Commission, companies, etc.

11.4 Disclosure of GenAI Usage

A complete declaration of GenAI usage must include the following information, presented in a clear and concise manner:

- **GenAI Tools (Applications or Models) and Specific Versions Used:** Indicate the name of the tool (e.g., "ChatGPT" for the application or "GPT" for the model) with reference to the specific version (e.g., "ChatGPT-4, version released March 2024"). If the precise model version is unavailable, the date of the query is acceptable. If multiple tools were used, specify each by name and version.
- **Date or Period of Use:** Specify the date or timeframe during which the tool was used (e.g., "Single use on October 13, 2024" or "Regular use from October 2024 to December 2024").
- **Specific Modes of Use:** Provide information on how the tool was utilized, linking it to the specific intended use case. For example: Specific Chapters, Sections, or Subsections where the Tool was Used: Specify exactly where the tool was applied. For example: "Generation of supporting charts in Chapter 2, Section 2.3," "Creation of a preliminary structure for Chapters 2, 3, and 4," "Creation of images and diagrams for the presentation of results in Slides 12-13," "Generation of the State of the Art in Paragraph 2 based solely on GenAI knowledge."

11.5 Placement and structure of the disclosure

The declaration of GenAI use must be placed in **easily identifiable positions** to ensure transparency regarding the tool's utilization. A "**layered approach**" may also be adopted, providing general information at the beginning of the document or material, accompanied by more specific details in dedicated sections.

12 Conclusions

The general principle of implementation of the project is that each partner undertakes to take part in the efficient implementation, and to cooperate, perform and fulfil, promptly and on time, all of its obligations under the Grant Agreement in a manner of good faith. This document is a guide providing all partners with a common and agreed framework of rules, procedures and tools that guarantee a smooth and collaborative implementation of the project.